

PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED SUPERMARKETS IN NAIROBI CITY COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract: This study ascertained how procurement management practices, specifically supplier relationship management, inventory management, contract management, and e-procurement adoption management affected performance of supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The variables selected were supported by stakeholder, resource-based view, and system theories. Descriptive design was deployed during the investigation. The population targeted comprised of 94 registered large and medium supermarkets in Nairobi County. The participants included procurement managers and officers at all 94 supermarkets in Nairobi City County composed of 282 participants. The survey employed all 282 participants utilizing census technique as the size of the sample. Utilizing questionnaires, primary data was acquired. Outcomes of the investigation displayed that Supplier Relationship Management practices significantly in a manner that is positive ($\beta = 0.202$) affects supermarkets performance in Nairobi City County, Kenya; inventory management practice positively ($\beta = 0.185$) affect performance of the supermarkets; contract management practice positively ($\beta = 0.135$) but affected the performance insignificantly of the supermarkets; while e-procurement adoption significantly affected supermarkets performance in a positive ($\beta = 0.299$) manner. The survey recommends that management of supermarkets should enhance their supplier management to boost the supermarkets performance. This would allow for building of a stronger relationship with the suppliers thus cutting down cost as a result of discounting fees.

Keywords: Supplier Relationship Management Practice, Inventory Management Practice, Contract Management Practice, E-procurement Adoption Management and Organizational Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Attributably to globalization, there is now more rivalry, shortage of resources, need for effectiveness and efficiency, desire for environmental preservation, and alterations in customer preferences and tastes. As a result of economies of scale and global sourcing, supermarkets offer a wider range of products at lower prices than small retailers and, in some cases, wholesalers (Nair & Chisoro, 2015). Supermarkets are also in a better position to provide their customers with additional services such as a one-stop shop where they can purchase all of their needs, packaging different collections of items being sold concurrently, and providing customers with value for their money (Odour, 2019).

Supermarkets have experienced significant growth and transformation globally. The expansion strategies of multinational retailers such as Wal-Mart, Carrefour, Metro, and Tesco have intensified competition in the supermarket format (Wu,

Chen, Hu & Xu, 2022). This growth is not confined to countries that are developed but also includes developing countries, where a food system transformation is occurring with the rapid growth of supermarkets (Reardon, Echeverria, Berdegué, Minten, Liverpool-Tasie, Tschirley & Zilberman, 2019). The biggest region in terms of global market for supermarkets in 2020 was North America, which accounted for 30% of the market. The second-largest region was Western Europe, which market share for supermarkets and hypermarkets worldwide was 26% and was the smallest in the Middle East on the world market ranking (Van Dam, Wood & Sacks, 2021). The distribution of the supermarkets across the different regions of the world is a reflection of the performance and the effectiveness of their procurement management which offers greater value of their customers.

African has also witnessed a tremendous spread of supermarkets with varying degree of dispersion. The mid-1990s witnessed supermarkets rise in Africa with its consequences agrifood systems and the rural poor (Barrett, Reardon, Swinnen & Zilberman, 2019). While supermarkets offer opportunities for farmers to access new markets and increase their income, there are concerns about the consolidation of power in the retail sector and its impact on small-scale retailers and farmers (Mwangi, 2019). Market concentration and market power are important factors to consider when analyzing the performance of supermarkets (Deconinck, 2021). Some countries, such as Tanzania, Burkina Faso, Malawi, and Ethiopia, have limited growth with very few supermarkets located in urban areas (Kussaga, Jacxsens, Tiisekwa & Luning, 2014).

Shopping in Sub-Saharan Africa combines formal and informal retail trade, modern and traditional, and a dynamic industry. In the first decade of the 1990s, formal retail trade was first introduced to the majority of Sub-Saharan Africa. The Sub-Saharan prospects viewed by retail chains commenced with new eyes as economies in the majority of countries liberalized to embrace market-based policies. Sub-Saharan Africa was referred to as "the next Asia" as its economies grew. With the rise of shopping malls, some nations are still establishing their formal retail industries, but others that had bright prospects for formalized retail a few years ago now have encouraging futures (Hugo, 2016). The South African consumer market is increasing quickly, and there has not been a commensurate infrastructural development, which has created the perfect environment for a creative and digitally based retail sector (Das Nair & Dube, 2017). In the past two decades, there exist a notable surge supermarkets numbers in Tanzania that are owned by South African retailers (Mohamed, 2019). Aside from that, Tanzania's contemporary shops are raising their rates and setting up shop in pricey malls. Accordingly, it's likely that the rise of contemporary stores in Tanzania is not motivated by affordable rates or the need to cater to low-income customers (Makori, 2020).

Due to growing customer information and new players entering the market, Kenya's retail sector is characterized by fierce and ongoing rivalry (Njoki, Kamau & Mbithi, 2019). The dynamic forces of a continually shifting competitive environment must be managed by the sector's businesses as a result of these challenges. Ochieng, Veetil and Qaim (2017) established that Uchumi, Nakumatt, Ukwalu, Naivas, and Tuskys are the most widespread Kenya's supermarket chains all Kenyan-owned have significantly been affected by risk of rejection and cost of delivery. Procurement practices advancement has resulted in significant growth in many Kenyan firms in terms of goods and service delivery to customers (Arachi, 2013).

The performance of procurement is critical to supermarket competitiveness. Because fair operations in supermarket were limited in Kenya, supermarkets have not implemented fully the practice of procurement. Kariuki (2013) contend that performance relates to the degree by which achieve their set goals and objectives. It pertains to the predetermined objectives or aims that make up the work parameters. The performance of procurement in Kenya is highly dependent on efficiency and efficacy of procedures involved in tendering (Kazi, 2012). Consequently, the primary achievement standard for any business is the generation of value, as defined by the resource supplier (Khang, Arumugam, Chong & Chan, 2010). The choice of practices of procurement is dependent on the firms' nature, their complexity, policies as well as value of the procurements (Makabira & Waiganjo, 2014).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The significance of supermarkets in the retail subsector cannot be overstated, however, recent poor performance is a concerning issue that needs attention (Aseyo *et al.*, 2018). To thrive in the face of dynamic environments of business, globalization, systematic risks, and surging local competition and foreign entrants, Kenyan supermarkets must develop their networks to offer diverse products that require substantial capital investment (Yang *et al.*, 2022). While diversifying their portfolios can minimize unsystematic risks, systematic risks cannot be managed through simple diversification, necessitating a deeper understanding of their impact on performance (Demmler *et al.*, 2017). Consequently, some

supermarkets have sought finance through equity financing, yet even with this funding, they have struggled and faced branch closures (Aseyo *et al.*, 2018).

The difficulties encountered by the Kenya grocery industry extend beyond financial concerns. Supply chain management poses a significant hurdle due to inadequate infrastructure, unreliable transportation, and limited access to quality suppliers (Mogire *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, consumer preferences and behavior play a crucial role, with changing trends and demands requiring supermarkets to adapt their offerings (Assis *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, the last-mile delivery problem presents obstacles such as a system of good national address that is lacking, concerns of traffic, issues of security, delivery high costs, and unreliable postal services (Mogire *et al.*, 2022).

Leading Kenyan supermarkets have been facing challenges and poor performance experience, which has led to the shutting down of businesses or a fall in branches number (Muturi, Omwenga & Owino, 2017). The large-sized supermarkets return on assets has been decreasing over the years which fell between 2016 and 2017, from 0.1418 to 0.1390, and between 2018 and 2019 from 0.1473 to 0.1446 indicating a decline in financial performance (Mwaura, 2019). The number of the branches closed down by big supermarket increased by 39.8 percent from 314 to 189 (Mboya, 2020). Similarly, medium-sized supermarkets have also experienced fluctuating return on assets (Lyu & Chen, 2022). Medium-sized supermarkets had a return on assets of 0.0810 in 2015; this figure rose to 0.0837 in 2016 and 0.920 in 2017. But in 2018 and 2019, this number dropped to 0.0893 and 0.0865, respectively. Even though other retail companies have profited from this, in 2020 there were only 13 new stores created and 125 branches closed. Additionally, international supermarket chains like Shoprite have closed their branches in Kenya due to underperformance (Lyu & Chen, 2022). The factors attributed to the poor performance of these supermarkets have been linked to lack of appropriate procurement technique management thus leading to non-satisfaction of customers in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The most affected supermarkets Nakumatt, Tuskys, Uchumi, Naivas and Quickmart.

Several studies examining the connection between procurement management practice and performances have been undertaken. Amoako-Gyampah (2018) established a significant effect of supplier relationships managements and firm performances in emerging economies. Simon and Chukwuemeziem (2018) also uncovered a significantly positive effect of inventory managements on organizational performances. Muhammed, Saoula, Issa and Ahmed (2019) demonstrated a substantial relationship between variables such as contract management and performance characteristics in Indonesia. Furthermore, Chepng'etich, Waiganjo, and Ismael (2020) unravel the significance of strategic supplier relationship and effectiveness of Kenya's decentralized government systems.

Although there exist a nexus between procurement management practice and performance, studies such as Chepng'etich, Waiganjo, and Ismael (2020); Sunmola and Shehu (2021); and Amahalu, Egolum, Ezechukwu, and Obi (2018) have conducted their researches in different context like government and food, thus providing a contextual gap for this study to fill. Additionally, Hajir (2021) examined how e-procurement procedures affected the operational effectiveness of Kenya's Nairobi City County Retail Supermarkets' study focused on e-procurement, this providing a conceptual gap. In addition, it is also noted that little studies have focused on supermarkets in Nairobi City County. Therefore, with these gaps most studies focused on other sectors providing a foundation for this study as it sought to determine how procurement managements practices affects the performances of Kenyan large and medium supermarkets in the City of Nairobi County.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1.3.1 General Objective

The general objective of the survey was to evaluate procurement management practices effect on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- i) To determine the influence of supplier relationship management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.
- ii) To assess the influence of inventory management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.
- iii) To determine the influence of contract management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

iv) To evaluate the influence of e-procurement adoption management on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

1.4 Research Questions

The research sought to answer these research questions:

i) What is the influence of supplier relationship management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya?

ii) What is the influence of inventory management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya?

iii) What is the influence of contract management practice on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya?

iv) What is the influence of e-procurement adoption management on performance of Supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Stakeholder's theory can be best described as a view, variety of ideas, metaphors and expressions relating to the stakeholders' value objectives. The theory originated from four lines of organizational research management which includes organizational theory, systems theory, strategic organizational planning and corporate social responsibility (Strand & Freeman, 2015). Managers should establish a modal centered on stakeholders' concept, according to Freeman (1984). The vocabulary was created by Freeman and other academics from around the globe in such a way that it discusses the issues of generating value and trade, the moral principles of capitalism, and administrative accountability market throughout the period of the 1980's and the 1990's. The stakeholder's theory further opined that the adoption of an analysis unit with regard to relationships between businesses and people can be affected by the above listed problems.

The management of the relationship between a stakeholder and the people involved in the business should be done by the executive (Freeman, 1984). When conflicts arise between a group of stakeholders, the conflict should be settled by the executives by finding a way to address the problems (Harrison, Bosse & Philips, 2010). Efficient management of the relationship that exists between stakeholders helps businesses to survive the test of time in most capitalist systems (Phillips, 2003). The stakeholder view has been globally utilized in a great number of disciplines such in such areas as government administration, legislation, policies regarding the environment, medical care, and morality (Freeman *et al.*, 2010). Stakeholder theory comprises of a variety of theories which involves a compilation of various normative values.

Resource Based View Theory was put forward by Barney (1991). RBV proposes that creative value propositions, exceeding customer expectations for the price paid, are key drivers of competitive advantage. The dominant research trend explores corporate resource identification and deployment strategies for achieving and sustaining this edge (Barney, 1991). Through the viability of local partnerships in emerging economies, or affiliates of their parent companies, global company strategists additionally clarify the accomplishments and failings of corporations across borders. To truly understand local value creation, tapping into the expert insights of an affiliate or forging a local partnership becomes a resource worth its weight in gold (Barney & Griffin, 1992). The Resource-Based View posits that companies possess unique and invaluable bundles of skills and assets, acting as potent weapons in the battle for long-term competitive advantage. As per the resource-based approach, a firm's competitive edge helps to increase organizational productivity and performance (Barney & Clark, 2007). It stated that organizational unique financial resources, human capital, skills, and technology provide a competitive edge for your company over rivals in achieving improved performance.

The system theory was put forward by von Bertalanffy (1950). This theoretical framework is predicated on the basis that an organization is whole, interdependence, hierarchy, openness and equifinality. The theory assumes that an organization is an organized whole, comprised of interrelated and interdependent components. This means that the system as a whole possesses properties that are not present in its individual parts. Systems theory concentrates more on three (3) basic stages of observation which includes the surroundings, the human members inside the corporation, and the social structure as a whole (Poole, 2014). This theory explains the interconnection with the organizational structures where no part of the organization operates in isolation thus leading to the organizational goals achievement. The systems theory is a discipline

that encompasses all natural, environmental, and scientific systems (Capra, 1997). Von Bertalanffy (1956) contrasted this definition by defining a system as a complex entity made up of interconnected parts. Systems theory aims to illuminate the dynamic interactions and interdependencies that exist among the different parts of the system. For an extended period, researchers in organizational studies were quick to embrace systems theory after realizing that traditional models were inadequate to explain intricate corporate actions. As awareness of the multifaceted nature of the work setting has grown, the systems theory's adoption has been possible (Ashmos & Huber, 1987).

2.2 Empirical Review

Studies were reviewed establishing the relationships between supplier relationship managements, inventory managements, contract managements and performance.

2.2.1 Supplier Relationship Management Practice and Organizational Performance

Amoako-Gyampah (2018) examined relationship managements with suppliers and business performances in emerging nations. Data was gathered from firms in Ghana with the aid of a questionnaire. The questionnaire respondents happened to work at senior levels for the companies. The study population comprised of senior managers from different companies in the Greater Accra Tema Metropolis Area and Sekondi-Takorandi area in Ghana. Two hundred and fifty (250) questionnaires were returned and of which only one hundred and forty-nine (149) were found useful. A three-factor measurement approach was used to assess the data's validity and dependability. At the conclusion of the study, it was determined that SRM had positively substantial impacts on the firms' performances. The earlier investigation was performed in Ghana thus providing contextual gap as Kenya was where the conduct of the current study took place.

Amedofu, Asamoah and Owusu (2019) examined effects of supplier relationship methods on Ghanaian start-up performances and customer developments. Data for the research project was gathered from Ghanaian startups. The questionnaire respondents include the founder of the start-up, CEOs sales executives and operational managers. Three hundred (300) start-ups respondents filled the questionnaire and of which only seventy-two (72) were selected useful for the study. SEM was applied to analyze the research models. Results showed relationships between supply chain managements and startup performances that is favorably significant. In the prior study, supply chain managements and its impacts on customer developments and startup performances were given more weight. This study was concentrated on supplier relationship managements and how it affects the performances of supermarkets thus providing a conceptual gap which this study filled.

Oduro, Nyarku and Gbadeyan (2020) carried out a study healthcare efficiency and supplier relationship managements in Ghana's expanding economy. Six thousand eight hundred and fifteen (6815) healthcare institutions in Ghana were used to collect the population for the research. These facilities included teaching medical facilities community-based wellness programs and services, hospitals, district medical centers, healthcare facilities midwives/maternity centers, and polyclinics. The cross-sectional design was deployed through the means of an explanatory survey. The study test models were conducted using quantitative research. Two hundred and thirty (230) hospitals were later selected with the utilization of simple random and convenience sampling techniques. A structural questionnaire was utilized in data garnering for the study with CEOs, purchasing managers, managers of marketing, and logistics supervisors as the questionnaire respondents. At the end of the study, the findings revealed supplier relationships managements dimensions. The performances of private hospitals in Ghana are profoundly affected beneficially by factors including interaction, collaboration, trust, environment, and adaptability. Also, cooperation, adaptation and atmosphere have a positively insignificant effect on public hospitals while communication and trust have a positively significant effect on public hospitals. The prior investigation, nevertheless, was limited to Ghanaian hospitals hence offering a contextual gap as supermarkets in Kenya was the subject of this study.

Chepng'etich, Waiganjo and Ismael (2020) investigated the performances of Kenya's decentralized forms of government on strategic supplier relationships. Through the application of both quantitative and qualitative models, adoption of cross-sectional survey approach was done. All personnel in the departments of finances and procurements make up the study population n Ten (10) Kenyan Counties which includes Garissa, Kisii, Nyamira, Narok, Kiambu, Muranga, Homabay, Marsabit and Bonnet. A stratified random selection method was used to get 166 responders out of a total of 186. Techniques like mean, median, standard deviation, SPSS, factor, and correlation analysis, the information obtained were examined. The study's conclusions showed that there is an advantageous correlation between strategic supplier relationships and the effectiveness of Kenya's devolved forms of government. Cross-sectional survey methodology was

adopted in the prior inquiry as methodological gaps were exposed while descriptive design was utilized for the current survey.

In Nairobi's flower businesses, Onyango and Litunya (2021) examined impacts of supplier managements on organizational performances. The audience for the research consisted of flower shops in Nairobi, and three participants from the nine enterprises that were chosen were employed. The investigation investigated the impact of supplier management's component of creating suppliers on the performance of organizations. Descriptive survey methodology was used in the study. Ten flower growers from Nairobi made up the study's population of samples. Top executives and managers in the procurement department were among the intended demographic. The target population of 10 floral companies yielded a sample of thirty participants. Utilization of questionnaires allowed for garnering primary data for the research. Pie graphs, illustrations, as well as tables of frequencies were used to display the research's findings. SPSS version 21.0 was utilized in evaluating quantitative data utilizing descriptive statistics to ascertain the relationship between parameters, it employed Pearson's product-moment correlation. The outputs uncovered that supplier development has considerable suitable impacts on Nairobi's flower enterprises' performances. The investigation's primary goal on flower businesses in Nairobi City County exposing the contextual gap as this survey was based on large and medium supermarkets on Nairobi City County.

2.2.2 Inventory Management Practice and Organizational Performance

Simon and Chukwuemeziem (2018) sought to examine the organizational effectiveness and inventory control at Dansa Food Limited in Lagos, Nigeria. To evaluate the inventory management, the research used descriptive survey. The Dansa group of companies in Ikeja, Lagos state, made up the research population. A purposeful non-probability sampling strategy was deployed in obtaining a total of two hundred and twenty (220) from the sample size, which was chosen at random. One sample T-test served as assessment of validity of research hypothesis, while research questions, descriptive statistics, and easy percentage approaches were employed to examine the information gathered from respondents. To gather information, an established questionnaire was used. At the conclusion of the investigation, it was discovered that inventory control significantly improves the organization's performance metrics. The previous study utilized purposive non-probability sampling technique while this survey utilized stratified random sampling technique. Despite the conduct of the survey, a contextual gap was exposed as the former was in Lagos with this having carried out in Nairobi City County.

Akinlabi, Asikhla and Obamiro (2018) researched how Nigerian flour milling firms' operational performance is affected by their inventory management techniques. All of the flour milling companies in Nigeria served as the research's core population, and all of the flour milling companies that are publicly traded on NSE served as its secondary population. Yet, the research's intended demographic consists of the 2,337 personnel who are in charge of overseeing the policy and management of inventory at the flour mills were chosen. The chosen companies received structured questionnaires. Using pilot research and exploratory factor analysis, reliability and validity tests took place. Data was descriptively and inferentially analyzed. The research's conclusions showed inventory shrinkage has inverse significant influences on customer satisfaction and inventory control and cost effectiveness have positive important effects. Only Nigerian flour milling enterprises were the subject of the study offering a contextual gap with the emphasis of the current investigation on supermarkets in Kenya.

Amahalu, Egolum, Ezechukwu and Obi (2018) investigated financial results and inventory control of breweries listed between 2010 and 2016 at Nigerian Stock Exchange. The survey used historical information that was gleaned from annual statements of finances and reports of companies listed on NSE. Ex-post facto design methodology was utilized. Seven (7) brewery firms listed made up the survey. The coefficients of correlation and ordinary least squares regression were utilized in data evaluation. The survey's conclusions showed significantly positive relationships of returns on assets with inventory conversion periods. In contrast to the previous study, which used historical data rather than more recent data, the current study used more recent data. Furthermore, the investigation disclosed contextual gap as the former was in Nigeria with this conducted in Kenya.

Agu, Obi-Anike and Eke (2018) unraveled the effects of inventory managements on organizational performances of manufacturing selected firms. The survey population size amounts to nine hundred and ninety-six (996). A sample size of two hundred and eighty-five (285) was obtained out of the nine hundred and ninety-six (996) study population size. Data obtained was with the use of a primary questionnaire and the conduction of an interview. Two hundred and eighty-five (285) questionnaires were issued out and distributed to various respondents and of which only two hundred and seventy

(270) copies were returned. A design based on descriptive survey research was used for the investigation. Utilizing correlation coefficient as well as simple linear regressions statistical techniques, the hypothesis was tested. The study's conclusions showed that there exist positive relationships of inventory control with productivity of chosen enterprises. The study however was conducted on manufacturing firms in Nigeria unraveling contextual gap which this present survey was conducted using supermarkets in Kenya.

Olanipon, Akinola, and Oladele (2022) analyzed the variables influencing the implementation of inventories/stock management methods in the tertiary medical centers in south-west Nigeria. They concentrated on each of the kinds of inventory management processes utilized there. To acquire data, a questionnaire was given to a sample of staff members from the pharmacies, department/supply, stock/inventory, as well as general department divisions. Considering these individuals are responsible for the colleges' entire inventory management procedures, these departments were specifically chosen. The gathered information was examined using descriptive and inferential statistics. According to the study, tertiary medical centers of Southwest Nigeria are aware of inventory managements strategies investigated, including EOQ, JIT, CR, and ABC analysis. It was further determined that implementation of inventory management strategies by tertiary health care providers of Southwest Nigeria was substantially affected by product categories, demand for products, as well as delivery time. This survey was performed in Nigeria where its procurement procedures are different from Kenya hence exposing a contextual gap.

2.2.3 Contract Management Practice and Organizational Performance

Brian (2018) examined the effectiveness of contract management on contractors' performances in Uganda. The researcher employed descriptive method of design. The population of the study involved forty (40) people which includes the procurement department members, user department, previous contract management members, human resource and administration and other employees working in Ministry of Trade, Industry and Cooperatives. Sample size consisted of thirty (30) respondents in total. The guide for interviews and questionnaires were the tools for collecting data. The survey found that actions and processes involved in contract management have favorable, significant impacts on contractors' performances. But Uganda was the location of the earlier investigation. As a result, Kenya was the location of the current investigation demonstrating a contextual gap.

Muhammed, Saoula, Issa and Ahmed (2019) investigated on contract management and performance characteristics in Indonesia. Through the adoption of qualitative approaches and structured questionnaires which were issued out and distributed, the target respondents were people from various public and private contracts. One hundred (100) questionnaires were distributed and only eighty-three (83) were recovered back. Out of the eighty-three (83) questionnaires which were gotten back, seventy (70) out of them were finally selected. The analysis was carried out with descriptive analysis while empirical association was carried out by means of regression analysis techniques. At the end of the survey, it was noticed that cost and benefit analysis have great significant effects on contract length while project delivery and quality have negative significant impacts on contract length. This study was carried out using qualitative data while quantitative data was used by this current study. More so, the context of the survey was in Indonesia with this having particular reference to Kenya.

By conducting empirical investigations into impacts of contract managements on Kiambu County's performances, Nyaga and Mwangangi (2019) aimed to close the gap. The following study goals served as a guide for the investigation: to ascertain the impact of contract connection management and contract cost management on the performances of Kiambu County. Quantitative approaches and descriptive survey design were utilized. 96 respondents were chosen as a sample for this investigation. The compelling evidence of this study underscores the significant performance gains associated with effective contract relationship management and diligent cost management. Kiambu County's path forward undoubtedly lies in prioritizing improved contract relationship practices. The survey targeted employees at Kiambu County, this study targeted procurement managers and supervisors in supermarkets in Nairobi City County. Although these investigations were performed in Kenya, they were contextually different from each other.

Matto, Ame and Nsimbila (2021) investigated the influences of contracts managements on Tanzania's cost-effectiveness procurement. In the study's data sourcing and analysis, quantitative technique was employed. For the study, a cross-sectional survey method was also implemented. The survey's data came from public sources in Tanzania's Dar es Salaam, Dodoma, and Arusha areas. The study data was gathered from one hundred and sixty-four (164) procurement entities was analyzed via inferential and statistical data that is descriptive. Findings indicated that contract creation and quality control are crucial elements that improve the financial value of Tanzanian public procurements. The aforementioned study only focuses on public money procurement in Tanzania while the recent study aimed majorly on supermarkets in Nairobi, Kenya providing both conceptual and contextual gaps.

Cherono and Chekwony (2021) addressed contracts management's practices effect on performances of road contractors in Nandi County, Kenya. The research implemented the usage of design which is descriptive. The survey's population entails two hundred (200) employees of the road construction projects, six (6) contractor's managers, thirty (30) ward administrators, thirty (30) members of the county assembly, one hundred and twenty (120) community members, two (2) staff of finance ministry and four (4) staff of the ministry of public work. The research also made use of three (3) sampling techniques for the respondents' selection which includes the stratified, sampling and purposive sampling techniques. The sample size consisted of one hundred and ninety-nine (199) respondents. Inference and descriptive techniques utilized for data evaluation. The result of the research revealed that contract monitoring, contract administration, contract relationship management and conflict management has effective effects on road contractor's performance. The former concentrated on roads contractors as this survey focused on supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

2.2.4 E-Procurement Adoption and Organizational Performance

To determine the motivators and barriers to implementation, Jayawardhena and Jayaratne (2019) looked into the adoption and performances of e-procurement in Sri Lanka's garment supply chain. Data were analyzed using exploratory, confirmatory factor analysis, and SEM. Results proved extensive effects on lowering costs, especially with regard to decreasing paperwork and associated mistakes, and enhancing the dependability and openness of the procurement process. Additionally, e-procurement led to a decrease in customer complaints, a decrease in reverse logistics expenses, a rise in fill rate, and a reduction in lead times. All stakeholders, notably clients, staff, and suppliers, were more satisfied as a result of the reduced workload. The effectiveness of e-procurement processes has been impeded by incompatibility, improperly established security systems, and lack of uniform technology across organizations. The study failed to look at the connection between supermarket performances and e-procurement adoptions thus providing conceptual difference.

Features of e-tendering systems' performances were examined from the users' point of view in a case study by Sunmola and Shehu (2021). From e-tendering literature, the design components were taken. Data from a survey using Kano questions were analyzed using a Kano model. It was found that the e-tendering platform's multiple-user, multi-language, limitless auctions time frame, free trial auctions, safety, real-time first interfaces, review capacity, and feedback indicated improved client satisfaction and absorption. Also, encouraging company engagement were elements like leadership oversight, honesty, conformity, and secrecy. Positive correlation between using e-tendering technology and improved business performance by keeping a customer-centered emphasis was discovered. This study employed multilinear regression models to analyze the study, which was conducted using the Kano model as this investigation was on OLS estimation model indicating the methodological gap.

The procedures of e-procurement effect on the operational effectiveness of Nairobi City County Retail Supermarkets in Kenya were examined by Hajir (2021). The study explored whether e-sourcing, e-tendering, and e-payments affected operational efficiency of Nairobi City County's retail supermarkets. The Technology Acceptance Model 2 served as foundation for the study. It was supported by the positivist philosophy, which demanded the use of quantitative methods. It took the form of a case study of Retail Supermarkets as a company or enterprise in Nairobi City County, Kenya. These methods involved interviewing the procurement managers at the store in Nairobi County and gathering primary data using provided questionnaires and interview guides. Regression analyses, descriptive statistics, and Spearman rank correlations were all used to assess the quantitative data that was gathered. The efficiency of operations of Nairobi City County's retail supermarkets was positively and statistically significantly impacted by e-procurement procedures, according to regression analysis. The report suggests that management make sure that implemented innovations are suitable with existing systems and resources in order to assure flexibility and usefulness. This study focused on not just e-procurement but also supplier relationships, inventory, and contract managements in addition to the study's previous focus on e-procurement practices tendering a conceptual gap filled by this survey.

Studies were conducted by Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha, and Restuputri (2021) to address how adoption of e-procurement has altered productivity of Indonesian manufacturing businesses. The four elements in this study are management support, information accuracy, e-procurement deployment, and business performance. Pilot testing surveys were used to see if participants understood the researcher's questions completely. Participants received the final survey after the initial assessment was finished. In order to determine the correlations between the factors, software such as SPSS version 21 and SmartPLS v3.0 were used to assess results of pilot tests and final surveys. Results of the investigation allow for the acceptance of three hypotheses. The results demonstrate that top management supports have important effects on the

deployment of e-procurement. The introduction of e-procurement is greatly affected by the quality of the information, and the business's success is considerably affected by the e-procurement adoption. The results of the investigation allow for the acceptance of three hypotheses. The results demonstrate that top management support has major impacts on deployments of e-procurement. The commencement of e-procurement has been significantly determined by the standard of the information, and the firm's performance is heavily impacted by the adoption of e-procurement, according to other research. This study focused on procurement managements practices, including supplier relationship, contract management, inventory management practices, and adoption of e-procurements, as opposed to the previous study's primary focus on e-procurement offering conceptual gap.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

As observed by Saunders and Lewis (2014), research design describes processes of population selection, data collection and data collection in providing answers to a research question. Kothari (2010) describes research design as a map and guideline that illustrates the process involved in providing solution to a research objective. Nelson (2014) posits that descriptive research design gives a clear description and solution to a research problem using charts and graphs. Therefore, the study adopted descriptive research design due to its unique capability when dealing with primary data (Creswell, 2014) to determine effects of procurement management practices on performances of Nairobi County's supermarkets in Kenya.

3.2 Target Population

The population targeted is a collection of components, incidents, people or families in which a researcher is interested in studying in order to extrapolate application (Kerlinger & Lee, 2007). The study targeted all of Nairobi City County's registered supermarkets. There are 94 retail supermarkets that are officially licensed and functioning (Retail Trade Association of Kenya, 2020).

3.3 Sampling Design

Sampling design is the mechanism through which samples are gathered for a study (Creswell, 2014). This is a subset of a target population which was employed for a survey (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2013). This study conducted a census where the entire respondent was drawn from all the supermarkets within the target population. Baffour, Chandra and Martinez (2019) noted that the application of census increase precision in the conclusion of an investigation.

3.4 Data Analysis and Presentation

The data evaluation was descriptively and inferentially performed. Descriptive statistics which include mean, frequency and percentage was used to perform basic analysis on the data gathered. Multiple regression analyses was utilized during inferential analysis to ascertain the effect of e-procurement adoptions, inventory managements practices, contract managements practices, and supplier relationship managements practices on performances of supermarkets in Nairobi County, Kenya. The result of the analysis was presented in charts and tables.

Regression model used is shown below;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Y =Organizational performance

B₀ = Constant

B₁, β₂, β₃= Coefficients of determination

X₁ = Supplier relationship managements practice

X₂ = Inventory management practice

X₃ =Contract managements practice

X₄= E-procurement adoption

ε = Error term

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Response Rate

The researcher utilized the data from Table 4.1, which included both responses and non-responses, to estimate the response rate of the survey participants. By examining the number of responses received in relation to the total number of individuals contacted, the researchers were able to calculate the proportion of individuals who provided a response.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Rates	Frequency	Percent
Response	214	75.9%
Non-Response	64	24.1%
Total	282	100

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The survey findings indicated that although not all participants' responses were obtained, the retrieved responses were deemed acceptable. It was observed that 24.1% of the survey participants chose not to respond, while 75.9% provided their input. Cooper and Schindler (2009) noted that the large number of recovered questionnaires offered adequate data for the survey analysis, which is sufficient for any investigation's analysis. This suggests that there was a partial non-response from the participants. However, Goodman and Pedersen (2022) argue that despite this limitation, the findings of the survey are still considered suitable and sufficient to justify further research into the responses.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

This section of the survey provides a concise summary of the results obtained from analyzing the relationships between the factors investigated. The survey findings are presented in Table 4.2, offering a clear and organized overview of the outcomes. This table serves as a valuable reference point for understanding the associations and connections between the factors examined in the inquiry.

Table 4.2 Correlation Results

		PERF	SRMP	IMP	CMP	EPA
PERF	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
SRMP	Pearson Correlation	.410**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
IMP	Pearson Correlation	.490**	.317**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
CMP	Pearson Correlation	.420**	.147*	.638**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.031	.000		
EPA	Pearson Correlation	.544**	.434**	.518**	.459**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The results of the correlation analysis, which examined the relationships between the variables in the experiment, were presented in Table 4.2. The findings revealed a significant and positive association between supermarket performance in Nairobi City County and the procurement practices, including supplier relationship management, inventory practices, contract practices, and e-procurement adoption. Although the strength of the correlations varied, all of the variables showed weak connections with supermarket performance, except for e-procurement adoption, which exhibited a moderate level of association in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

4.3 Regression Results

The model summary, including the Adjusted R square and R square values, is presented in Table 4.3. This table provides a concise overview of the model's performance and the amount of variance explained by the predictors. The Adjusted R square and R square values serve as indicators of the model's goodness of fit and its ability to account for the variability in the dependent variable.

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.679 ^a	.519	.506	.54220

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The performance of supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya, exhibited a positive correlation with various procurement practices, including supplier relationship management, inventory practices, contract practices, and e-procurement adoption. This positive relationship was reflected in an R-value of 0.679. However, the R-square value of 0.519 indicated that only 51.9% of the variation in supermarket performance could be attributed to these procurement practices. This means that 51.9% of the changes in supermarket performance were collectively influenced by the aforementioned factors. It is important to note that the remaining 48.1% of the performance variation was not accounted for by the examined procurement practices. These findings highlight the significant impact of procurement practices on supermarket performance, while also indicating that other factors beyond the scope of the survey may contribute to the remaining performance variation.

4.4 Analysis of Variance

The results of the statistical analysis of variance, aimed at determining the on the whole model significance, were illustrated in Table 4.4. This table provides a comprehensive overview of the outputs obtained from the analysis.

Table 4.4 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	30.902	4	7.726	33.806	.000 ^b
	Residual	47.762	209	.229		
	Total	78.664	213			

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The outputs of the variance analysis are presented in Table 4.4, providing insights into the significance of the model. The F-value, which signified the extent to which the predictors have a significant impact, was utilized to assess the performance of supermarkets as the explained factor. A notable F value of 33.806 was observed, indicating a significant effect. The outcomes were further confirmed by a p-value of 0.000, surpassing the supposed significance level of 5%. This signifies that the joint impact of procurement practices significantly affects supermarkets performance.

4.5 Multiple Regression Analysis

To assess the variables effect such as supplier relationship management, inventory practices, contract practices, and e-procurement adoption on the performance of supermarkets, regression analysis was employed. The outputs linked to the effect of each factor on the discussed components are presented in Table 4.5, providing substantial evidence to support the outputs derived from the analysis.

Table 4.5: Regression Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.321	.153		2.096	.037
	SRMP	.204	.061	.202	3.319	.001
	IMP	.194	.079	.185	2.458	.015
	CMP	.116	.062	.135	1.865	.064
	EPA	.325	.075	.299	4.345	.000

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Considering the parameter estimates presented in Table 4.16, the regression equation can be expressed as follows;

$$PERF = 0.321 + 0.202SRMP + 0.185IMP + 0.135CMP + 0.299EPA + \varepsilon$$

Where: PERF = Performance; SRMP = supplier relationship management practice; IMP = Inventory management practice; CMP = Contract management practice; EPA = E-procurement adoption

4.6 Interpretation of Findings

The outcomes of the survey provided insights into the factors that contribute to Nairobi City County's performance of supermarkets. The standardized beta values indicated the relative importance of each factor in explaining supermarket performance. The regression intercept estimate yielded a positive value of 0.321, with a corresponding p-value of 0.037, which falls below the significance threshold of 0.05. This proposed that the intercept is statistically significant and contributes to the explanation of supermarket performance.

According to the survey's findings, supplier relationship management practices exhibited a significant positive (0.202), with a p-value of 0.001. This indicates that an improvement in supplier relationship management practices would lead to an enhancement in supermarket performance. The null assertion, which suggested that supplier relationship management practices has insignificant effect on supermarket performance, was rejected based on these results. The result supports the conclusion of Amoako-Gyampah (2018) who concluded that SRM had positively substantial impacts on the performances of the firms. Amedofu, Asamoah and Owusu (2019) also showed relationships between supply chain managements and startup performances that are favorably significant. Chepng'etich, Waiganjo and Ismael (2020) reached a conclusion that there is an advantageous of strategic supplier relationships with the effectiveness of Kenya's devolved forms of government. Onyango and Litunya (2021) unraveled that supplier development has considerable suitable impacts on Nairobi's flower enterprises' performances.

The survey findings revealed a significant positive coefficient effect (0.185) of inventory management practices on supermarket performance, surpassing the significance threshold of 0.05 percent. This indicates that enhancing inventory management practices in supermarkets would positively impact their performance in Nairobi City County. The null hypothesis, which assumes no significant effect of inventory management practices on supermarket performance, was rejected as per the non-difference hypothesis. Therefore, it can be concluded that inventory management practices significantly determined the supermarkets performance. The outcome aligned with Simon and Chukwuemeziem (2018) discovered that inventory control significantly improves the organization's performance metrics. Amahalu, Egolum, Ezechukwu and Obi (2018) obtained a significantly positive effect returns on assets on inventory conversion periods. Agu, Obi-Anike and Eke (2018) unfolded the existence of positive link of inventory control with productivity of chosen manufacturing enterprises.

The effect of contract management practice on supermarket performance was found to be positive, with a coefficient of 0.135. However, the survey outcomes supported the null claim, indicating that contract management practice has insignificant effect on supermarket performance, as affirmed by 0.064 p-value which exceeds the significance 0.05 threshold. This suggests that contract management practice has an insignificant impact on the performance of supermarkets in Nairobi City County, Kenya. The outcome aligned with Nyaga and Mwangangi (2019) uncovered significantly positive effect of managing contract relationships and managing costs on performance. Matto, Ame and Nsimbila (2021) indicated that contract creation and quality control are crucial elements that improve the financial value of Tanzanian public procurements. Cheron and Chepwony (2021) revealed that contract monitoring, contract administration, contract relationship management and conflict management has effective effects on road contractor's performance.

The adoption of e-procurement in Nairobi County positively influences the performance of supermarkets, as signified by an effect of 0.299 value. Contrary to the hypothesis suggesting that e-procurement adoption has insignificant effect on supermarket performance in Nairobi County, the evidence gathered from the outcomes rejects the null argument. The p-value of 0.000, which is below the significance 0.05 threshold, demonstrates that contract management practices indeed has significantly affected on supermarket performance. This finding aligns with Sunmola and Shehu (2021) unfolded a positive nexus of using e-tendering technology with improved business performance by keeping a customer-centered emphasis. Hajir (2021) discovered that the efficiency of operations of retail supermarkets was positively and statistically significantly impacted by e-procurement procedures. Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha, and Restuputri (2021) found that the commencement of e-procurement has been significant by the standard of the information, and the firm's performance is heavily impacted by the adoption of e-procurement.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The outcomes of the survey revealed that procurement management practices, including supplier relationship management, inventory management, contract management, and e-procurement adoption, had diverse impacts on the performance of supermarkets. The results specifically highlighted the significant and positive supplier relationship

management practices effect on Nairobi City County's supermarket performance. This underscores the importance of effective practices in driving the supermarkets' performance in the area. Based on this outcome, supplier relationship management practices significantly affect the Kenyan performance of supermarket in Nairobi City County.

The survey's findings aligning with its objectives revealed a significant and positive inventory management practices effect on Kenyan supermarkets' performance in Nairobi City County, Kenya. Therefore effective management of inventory performs a vital role in evaluating the performance of supermarkets. The survey concludes that the performance of supermarkets is significantly influenced by inventory management practices in Kenya's Nairobi City County.

The outputs pertaining to contract management practices indicate a positive but insignificant impact on Nairobi City County's supermarkets performance in Kenya. As pertains to the survey's objectives, it is evident that contract management practices have minimal influence on how supermarket performance is evaluated. In conclusion, contract management practices do not significantly contribute to the performance of supermarkets in the area under investigation.

The survey findings provided compelling evidence that the adoption of e-procurement in supermarkets within Nairobi City County, Kenya, positively impacts their performance. These results strongly indicate that the influence of e-procurement adoption on supermarket performance is significant. Therefore, increasing the adoption of e-procurement practices has the potential to greatly enhance the supermarkets performance.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

The survey recommends that the supplier relationship management practices should be enhanced to boost the performance of supermarkets. This would allow for building of a stronger relationship with the suppliers thus cutting down cost as a result of discounting fees. The management of the supermarket needs to ensure that inventories are effectively managed to improve the supermarkets performance. This would allow for the availability of the needed products thus reducing the level of customers' disappointment in the face of lacking products available. It is advised that the management of these supermarkets should carefully review the terms and conditions of their contracts to optimally achieve performance in Kenya. The survey suggests that the management of these supermarkets need to deploy all resources available to install e-procurement facilities that would create convenience for the customers thus satisfying their needs which in turn lead to optimal performance of the supermarkets.

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